

SOCIOLOGY

SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP SCOTT HARRISON, CHARITY:WATER

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Abstract

In this article, the author considers social entrepreneurship as a modern type of organization that can actively participate in the fight against global problems. The paper focuses on the characteristics of social entrepreneurship discussed in the existing literature, and the author suggests an additional feature of modern social entrepreneurship as the need for close interaction with public authorities. As a vivid example of modern social entrepreneurship, the author considers the Charity:Water organization.

Keywords: social entrepreneurship, global problems, social mission.

Due to the essential need for solving global problems, the concept of social entrepreneurship is gaining attention in the modern world. However, the phenomenon of social entrepreneurship is not new (Dees, 1998). And it has been actively discussed in the academic literature since the term “social entrepreneurship” was first suggested by Drayton B. when he established the Ashoka foundation in 1980 (Sen, 2007). The academic writers emphasize the presence of a socially useful mission as the common feature of social entrepreneurship (Cornwall, 1998; Hibbert et al., 2001; Dees, 1998). Scholars also mention innovativeness as one of the characteristics of social enterprises (Drucker, 1985, p.23; King, 1987; Borins, 2000) as well as resourcefulness (Stevenson, 1985), recognizing new opportunities and accountability of value creation (Sullivan et al., 2003). Dees gathered all these features to define the “ideal” social entrepreneurship. However, the recent academic literature more often discusses the importance of interaction between social entrepreneurship and state authorities. The reason may be that social entrepreneurship in part helps governments fulfill their functions to improve the life of the population and combat acute problems (Bornstein et al., 2010, p.99). Therefore, besides the described earlier features of social entrepreneurship, an ideal modern one may also be characterized by the ability to bilaterally interact with local and public authorities in order to achieve a common social goal. The features of social entrepreneurship which were earlier emphasized in the literature and also the new idea of interaction with the authorities may be applied to the organization called “Charity:Water”. The organization solves a global modern problem of lack of clean water and may be named the bright example of modern social entrepreneurship. The work considers the characteristics of social entrepreneurship discussed in the existing literature and the idea of the necessity of interaction with public authorities as an additional feature of modern social entrepreneurship using the example of Charity:Water.

The main feature of social entrepreneurship is the presence of a socially useful goal and the orientation of activity towards improving the well-being of society. For a social entrepreneur a public goal becomes central (Peredo et al., 2006). According to Dees (1998), social entrepreneurs do not focus on financial gain for individuals but aim at providing wealth for society. They do not aim at short-term projects to achieve success and revenue but focus on creating long-term improvements in the world. However, the organizational form of SE is also unique as it may be a hybrid that has both for-profit and non-profit characteristics (Alter, 2006; Townsend and Hart, 2008). Despite that, it should allocate most of its gained profit towards the maintenance of the operation and achievement of a social mission (Kerlin, 2010). The ability to gain profit and the mission are the most important features which distinguish social entrepreneurship from classic NGOs/NPOs and other businesses respectively. Some commercial organizations which want to participate in social issues may use such a way of involvement as Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). However, they can't be called social entrepreneurs as their main missions are not social. Moreover, according to Doane (2005), such organizations are mostly interested in CSR as a tool for reaping the financial benefits of ethical consumerism and improving relationships with both the public and government rather than an instrument of positive influence on society. Thus, social entrepreneurship distinguishes itself from other types of organizations by its social mission and the ability to gain profit mostly directed on covering its expenses.

Despite the ability of social entrepreneurship to gain profits, Charity:Water chose a non-profit path for the achievement of its main goal (Charity: Water, 2019). Its mission is to prevent the diseases caused by dirty drinking water and enrich the population of the planet with clean water. The organization does not have any commercial activities but receives large investments from private companies and donators. In 2017

the company raised \$50 million and invested \$45.4 million in water projects, while the rest covered its operational expenses. By 2002 they have already funded around 51,500 water projects that provided clean water to more than 11 million people around the world (Charity: Water, 2019). Thus, the organization is continuing to pursue its social mission raising the number of areas with access to basic human needs.

A social organization can't be called entrepreneurship if it does not have an innovative idea in its operation. Schumpeter (1934, p.66) argued that entrepreneurs are innovators whose main function is to change the production structure. He said that entrepreneurs drive the economy by entering new markets and applying new methods of using things. They do not have to invent something; they can make use of innovation or improve an existing product (Drucker, 1985, p.42). However, Drucker (1985, p.26-31) argued that entrepreneurs are not always connected with specific technologies or products; they can just be the force to significant changes in social, economic, banking, educational, technological and other spheres. Johnson (2000, p.1) takes the same approach and defines entrepreneurship as «emerging as an innovative approach for dealing with complex social needs». The Schwab Foundation (2002, p.56) makes an accent that entrepreneurial innovations may be directed especially at marginalized and poor people.

The organization "Charity: Water" is a good example of these approaches as it touches on the innovative idea of the fight against inequality and lack of water for poor people. The organization does not invent any new technology for building wells in poor regions but the idea of focusing on the problem of lack of water on a large scale is unique. Moreover, the organization is distinguished by its innovative campaign to inspire people to participate in charity. Charity:Water gives 100% of the full amount of donation to funding its water projects that motivate lay people to become change makers. As evidence of its integrity, the organization applies innovative technologies which enable every donor to remotely follow the project he (she) invested in. Thus, Charity:Water may be called entrepreneurship for its innovative approaches to operations and providing services.

Besides innovativeness and a social mission, the ability to recognize the opportunity for making global changes is also necessary for a potential social entrepreneur. Drucker (1985) emphasizes that "the entrepreneur always searches for change, responds to it, and exploits it as an opportunity" (p.33). Martin et al. (2007) support Drucker's idea but clarify that a social entrepreneur's opportunity leads to the achievement of social goals. Austin et al. (2006) separate the social entrepreneur and the commercial entrepreneur, emphasizing that the former finds and applies the opportunities that benefit society, and the latter recognizes the opportunities that bring him personal profit. However, Weerawardena et al. (2006) argue that opportunity-seeking is closely connected with the financial resources of entrepreneurship as its opportunity boundaries expand with the growth of an organization's budget.

Scott Harrison's experience as a volunteer on the Mercy Ships in Africa helped him to feel the acute social problem and identify financial possibilities for solving it. He managed to attract an audience to the problem using such an efficient entrepreneur's method of engaging people as storytelling (Bornstein, 2010). As the evidence of charitable use of funds, Charity:Water provides the philanthropists with photos and GPS of the projects. Of its transparency and high accountability people who want to participate in charity trust the organization and invest in water projects. As the result, the organization's resources annually increase and the number of projects rises.

As recent cases show, launching projects, effective management, and raising funds are not possible without active interaction and support from state governments. Wolk (2007) points to the benefits for society of the collaboration between government and social entrepreneurship (p.5) and gives numerous examples of successful interactions (p.39-43). As in most cases, modern social entrepreneurship fully or partially depends on the governments (Stephan et al., 2015), active support becomes a necessity. Santos (2009, p.17) examines the role of social entrepreneurship in a modern economy based on market capitalism, emphasizing the importance of government regulation and support for social entrepreneurship. The author gives an example of the French social entrepreneurship "Unis-Cite", which was able to achieve tremendous growth only when the French government recognized the importance of the organization's mission and then legislatively and financially supported it (Santos, 2009, p.24). Consequently, modern successful social entrepreneurship can also be characterized by the presence of collaboration with the state in order to achieve a common social goal. However, Weerawardena et al. (2006) suggest that if a not-for-profit organization fully depends on the government, in this case, it becomes the "service provider arm of government". The organization may feel uncertain about its financial future and does not have the whole control over the development of its projects. Thus, the ideal situation for non-profit organizations may be to balance government funding and other ways of funding.

Charity:Water does not publish information on state financial support, since projects are mainly funded by private donors (Charity: Water, 2019). However, the organization actively interacts with the governments of countries and regional leaders that play an important role in the implementation of water projects. The reason for that is that Charity:Water helps local governments to fulfill their main functions in providing the population with basic needs without burdening their budgets. Local governments are responsible for keeping the wells in working condition; they stimulate the growth of human resources, which will be involved in the further maintenance and repair of wells (Charity: Water, 2019). Thus, the establishment of cooperation of the organization with state and local authorities is an important step towards achieving the social mission as it benefits all the participants of the interaction: the organization, communities, and the governments.

Social entrepreneurship has been particularly active in recent years, which may be a result of increased concern about global problems. Social entrepreneurship is one of the methods which aims at eliminating social problems. Social mission is a distinctive feature of social entrepreneurship from other types of organizations (Dees, 1998). The presence of innovative ideas and opportunities for implementing social missions are also often highlighted in determining ideal social entrepreneurship by researchers in the academic literature (Johnson, 2000; Borins, 2000). However, the authors of academic papers miss the characteristic of cooperation with the public sector, which is so important in the modern economy. Indeed, the development of social entrepreneurship in a specific region may be possible if the goals of the state coincide with the goal of the organization (Wolk, 2007). The organization "Charity: Water" was considered as an example that meets all the above-mentioned characteristics of social entrepreneurship. The organization's activity may also confirm the importance and the necessity of collaboration with state and local governments in the implementation of social projects.

References

1. Alter, S. K. (2006). Social enterprise models and their mission and money relationships. In A. Nicholls (ed.) *Social entrepreneurship: New models of sustainable social change*, pp. 205—232. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press
2. Austin, J., Stevenson, H., and Wei-Skillern, J. (2006). Social and commercial entrepreneurship: Same, different, or both? *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 30(1), pp.1—22
3. Borins, S. (2000). Loose cannons and rule breakers, or enterprising leaders? Some evidence about innovative public managers. *Public Administration Review*, 60, pp.498—507
4. Bornstein, D., Davis, S., (2010). *Social Entrepreneurship: What everyone needs to know*. Oxford University Press
5. Charity: Water, (2019). [online] Available at: <https://uk.charitywater.org/> (Accessed 6 Nov. 2019)
6. Cornwall, J. (1998). The entrepreneur as building block for community. *Journal of Developmental Entrepreneurship*, 3(2), pp.141—148
7. Dees, J. G. (1998). The meaning of social entrepreneurship». Stanford University: Draft Report for the Kauffman Centre for Entrepreneurial Leadership
8. Doane, D. (2005). The myth of CSR. *Stanford Social Innovation Review* (Fall), pp. 22—29.
9. Drucker, P.F. (1985). *Innovation and entrepreneurship: practice and principles*. London: Routledge, 2015
10. Hibbert, S. A., Hogg, G., and Quinn, T. (2001). Consumer response to social entrepreneurship: The case of the Big Issue in Scotland. *International Journal of Nonprofit and Voluntary Sector Marketing*, 7, pp.288—301
11. Johnson, S. (2000). *Literature Review on Social Entrepreneurship*. Research Associate, Canadian Centre for Social Entrepreneurship
12. Kerlin, J.A. (2010). A comparative analysis of the global emergence of social enterprise. *Voluntas: International Journal of Voluntary and Nonprofit Organizations*, 21 (2), pp. 162—179
13. King, P. J., & Roberts, N. C. (1987). Policy entrepreneurs: Catalysts for policy innovation. *Journal of State Government*, 60, pp.172—178
14. KPMG International (2014). *Sustainable Insight: Unlocking the value of social investment*. Available at: <https://assets.kpmg/content/dam/kpmg/pdf/2014/05/unlocking-value-social-investment.pdf>
15. Martin, R.J., and Osberg, S. 2007. *Social Entrepreneurship: The Case for a Definition*. *Stanford Social Innovation Review*, pp.29—39.
16. Peredo, A., and McLean, M. (2006). Social entrepreneurship: A critical review of the concept. *Journal of World Business*, 41(1), pp.56-65.
17. Santos, F. M. (2012). A positive theory of social entrepreneurship. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 111(3), pp.335—351
18. Sen, P. (2007). Ashoka's big idea: Transforming the world through social entrepreneurship. *Futures*, 39(5), pp.534-553
19. Schumpeter, J.A. (1943). *The theory of economic development: an inquiry into profits, capital, credit, interest, and the business cycle*. Translated from the German by Redvers Opie; with a new introduction by John E. Elliott. New Brunswick, New Jersey: Transaction Books, 1983
20. Stephan, U., Uhlaner, L.M., and Stride, C. (2015). The role of institutional voids, institutional support, and institutional configurations. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 46, pp.308—331
21. Stevenson, H.H., and Gumpert, D.E. (1985). *The Heart of Entrepreneurship*. *Harvard Business Review*, March-April, pp. 85-94
22. Sullivan Mort, G., Weerawardena, J., and Carnegie, K. (2003). Social entrepreneurship: Towards conceptualization. *International Journal of Nonprofit and Voluntary Sector Marketing*, 8(1), pp.76—88
23. The Schwab Foundation. (2002). *Outstanding social entrepreneurs 2002*. Geneva, Switzerland: The Schwab Foundation for Social Entrepreneurship
24. Townsend, D.M., and Hart, T.A. (2008). Perceived Institutional Ambiguity and the Choice of Organizational Form in Social Entrepreneurial Ventures. *Sage Journals*.
25. Weerawardena, J., and Mort G.S. (2006). Investigating social entrepreneurship: A multidimensional model. *Journal of World Business*, 41, pp.21-35
26. Wolk, A.M. (2007). *Social Entrepreneurship and Government: A New Breed of Entrepreneurs Developing Solutions to Social Problems*. *The Small Business Economy: A Report to the President*, The Small Business Administration, Office of Advocacy